

Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt(II) by Adsorption of its 1-Hydroxy-1-phenyl-3-benzyl-2-thiourea Complex on Microcrystalline Naphthalene

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Manuscript received 17 November 1993, revised 7 April 1994, accepted 23 May 1994

A method for the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt(II) by adsorption of its 1-hydroxy-1-phenyl-3-benzyl-2-thiourea (HPBT) complex on microcrystalline naphthalene has been developed in the pH range 3.0-6.5. The complexation between the hydroxy substituted thioureas and metal ions is attributed to the availability of the oxime and thio-keto groups. Several metals have been separated by adsorption of their complex on microcrystalline naphthalene¹. HPBT-Co^{II} complex is rapidly and quantitatively adsorbed on microcrystalline naphthalene in the aqueous phase. The adsorbed naphthalene crystals were separated by filtration process, dried and dissolved in dimethylformamide (DMF). The absorbance of the solution was measured at 450 nm against the reagent blank. Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range of 5-80 µg of Co^{II} in 10 ml DMF. The apparent molar absorptivity was found to be $2.75 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The effects of pH reagent concentration and diverse metals ions were investigated too.

Results and Discussion

The sample solution containing 50 µg of Co^{II} and 3 ml of HPBT at pH 5.0 was digested for 3 min at 40-50° and Co^{II} extracted by adsorption on naphthalene, dried and dissolved in DMF solution. Its absorbance was measured at 450 nm at which the reagent blank had negligible absorbance. For complete adsorption of the complex, 3 ml naphthalene solution was enough. Adsorption is very fast at 40-50°. Ten samples of solution containing 50 µg of Co^{II} were analysed which provided a mean ab-

sorbance of 0.482 with a standard deviation of 0.016%.

The effect of various diverse metal ions, i.e. Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}, Mn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Fe^{III}, Al^{III}, Cr^{III}, Pt^{IV} and V^V were examined into the solution of the Co^{II} complex of HPBT containing 50 µg of Co^{II}. Interference due to overlapping of absorption bands may be eliminated by the addition of acid which will cause labile metal complexes to dissociate but not the cobalt complex. The other transition metals did not seriously interfere in the system, nor did alkali and alkaline earth metals.

Experimental

A standard stock solution of Co^{II} (1000 ppm) was prepared by dissolving requisite amount of hydrated cobalt perchlorate in distilled water. The stock solution was further diluted as required. A 0.2% solution of HPBT in ethanol and 20% naphthalene solution in acetone were prepared. Buffer solution was prepared by mixing equal volume of 1 M acetic acid and 1 M ammonium acetate for pH 5.0. All chemical used were of spectrograde quality. An E.C. G.S. 5701 spectrophotometer was used for all the absorbance measurements. Measurements of pH were made with a Systronic 335 pH meter.

An aliquot containing 5-80 µg of Co^{II} was pipetted into a flask and diluted to 50 ml with distilled water. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5 with acetate buffer solution (4 ml) and then 0.2% HPBT solution (3 ml) was added. Contents

of the flask were mixed thoroughly and heated on a water-bath at 40–50°. Then 20% naphthalene solution (3 ml) were added and shaken vigorously for 3 min. The metal complex was rapidly adsorbed on naphthalene. It was filtered off, washed with distilled water, dried and the solid mass was dissolved in DMF (10 ml). The absorbance of the solution was measured at 450 nm against the reagent blank.

References

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